

XRF

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 209.**

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XRF-ANALYSIS OF SAMPLES IN SOLID FORM			

1 SUMMARY

Solid samples can be analyzed with the application Wroxi.

Inhomogeneous samples (e.g. samples with lumps) must be grided before sample preparation.

The calibration includes the following oxides: SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Na₂O, K₂O, CaO, SrO, BaO, Fe₂O₃, Mn₃O₄, MgO, P₂O₅, SO₃, V₂O₅, Cr₂O₃, ZrO₂, NiO, CuO, ZnO, PbO, HfO₂, TiO₂

2 GENERAL INFORMATION

Samples containing pure metals cannot be analyzed by this method.

Concentration ranges for different oxides are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Concentration ranges (%) for different oxides, referring to 0,8 g of sample

Al₂O₃	CaO	Fe₂O₃	K₂O	MgO	Na₂O	P₂O₅	SiO₂
0-80	0-80	0-80	0-40	0-80	0-60	0-40	0-100
BaO	Cr₂O₃	CuO	NiO	PbO	TiO₂	SrO	SO₃
0-40	0-10	0-8	0-10	0-10	0-60	0-40	0-60
V₂O₅	Zn₂O	ZrO	HfO				
0-10	0-10	0-45	0-10				

Solid materials are first dried at 105°C until no further loss of weight occurs (if nothing else is specified by the customer).

A copy of this instruction can be found in folder 8 in the XRF laboratory.

3 HAZARDS AND SAFETY

Always use protective goggles, gloves and laboratory clothing. Ensure good ventilation when working with lithium borate.

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4 QUALITY ASSURANCE OF ANALYTICAL METHOD

4.1 Drift control:

Three different glass disks (Quality Material, QM), made from Certified Reference Material (CRM) are used for drift control of the Wroxi application.

LIMS-ID:

33100, QM XRF Sol (made from 22334)

33153, QM XRF P Ca (made from 24411)

33155, QM XRF Fe (made from 22845)

The three QM are analyzed every Monday, using the Wroxi application.

Create a run in LIMS with the three QM as control samples.

Enter the results in LIMS. The concentrations should be within the acceptance limits, e.g., within 2xstdev.

The following measures are taken if any concentration is out of the acceptance limits:

- Re-analyze the QM that is out of acceptance limits.
- Re-analyze the last CRM glass disk of the same type

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If the result is still not acceptable, run the monitor sample.

Important: make a data backup before the monitor is analyzed.

Read section 10.1 before proceeding.

4.2 Drift correction using monitor

Make a drift correction for the elements of interest, make sure to use the right monitor.

4.2.1 There are four different monitor samples:

BGSMON and FLX S13: delivered together with the Wroxi standard.

PB2 and PC3: purchased especially to be used for Fe ore and phosphate ore

- PB2 for the correction of Fe, Mn and Ti
- PC3 for the correction of P och Si

4.2.2 Insert the BGSMON and other monitors to be used into the XRF instrument.

Run monitor for the application Wroxi

Important: if a monitor contains elements for which no drift correction is needed, their drift factors can be fixed before running the monitor. This procedure is only allowed if the result for a freshly made CRM sample is in accordance with the certificate.

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4.2.3 Correction

After running the monitor, all QM must be re-analyzed. The results must be within the acceptance limits, also for the last sample that was prepared. If the results are still not within the acceptance limits, follow the procedures for troubleshooting in section 10.1.2-10.1.3 and 10.2.

4.3 Control with CRM: a control with a CRM suitable for the sample type of interest is performed every second month:

SARM 32: CRM for phosphate ore

Nist 690 Iron ore: CRM for Fe ore

BCS-RM No 201a: CRM for silica,

All glass disk samples should be labelled with date of preparation and saved.

4.4 If the surface of the mold is scratched or dull, polish the surface for better luster. Polishing should be followed by running a fusion with only powder flux.

4.5 Additional data backup should be done before every change in store data.

5 APPARATUS

Fusion instrument (LeNeo, Claisse), crucibles and mold

XRF instrument (Zetium, Malvern Panalytical), with associated computer software (SuperQ)

Balance with four digit precision

6 CHEMICALS

Prefused flux; Lithium Borate: LiT/LiM/LiI 66,67/32,83/0,5

CRM; certified reference material for phosphate ore, iron ore and silica

Citric acid for rinsing of crucibles

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7 PROCEEDURE

- 7.1 Weigh 0,8000g of sample in a platinum curible
- 7.2 Weigh 8,0000g ($\pm 0,0005$) of prefused flux in the crucible
- 7.3 Mix well, preferrably using a wortex
- 7.4 Insert the crucible in the fusion instrument and run the fusion program Wroxii de chauffe 2
- 7.5 Analyze the glass disk with the XRF instrument, using the application WROXI in SuperQ.

For operation of the XRF instrument, see instruction APP 002

8 CALCULATING AND REPORTING

Results should be reported with one digit precision, except for mining and RD&I samples that should be reported with two digits precision.

Results can be imported to LIMS.

Important! The LIMS data import only functions for data delimited by the comma symbol, not with the period symbol.

9 WASTE DISPOSAL

Glass disks can be disposed in the glass container.

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10 ADDITIONAL INSTRUCTIONS

- 10.1 Troubleshooting when a result of a QM is not within the acceptance limits:
- 10.1.1 Fuse two new glass disks of the QM, and analyze them with the Wroxi application. The results should be within the acceptance limits.
- 10.1.2 If results are still not within the acceptance limits, inspect the run for possible errors. Check the raw counts for rapid changes, and that the "compensation factor" is reasonable.
- 10.1.3 If there is a suspected error in previous measurements, fix the error and re-run the monitor. If the results are now within the acceptance limits, re-analyze all samples that have been analyzed since the error first occurred.
- 10.2 Re-calibration of the method: a re-calibration is performed if the problem cannot be solved in any other way.
- 10.2.1 Inspection of the calibration curve: Error in the calibration curve can be traced by checking the counts for the most concentrated calibration standard. Analyze glass disks that were used for the highest calibration point in the original calibration. Compare the derived concentrations with the known concentration. If there is no difference between derived concentration and known concentration, re-calibration cannot solve the problem. If there is a difference, proceed to the next section.
- 10.2.2 Re-calibration
 Insert the glass disks used as calibration standards in the XRF instrument. Analyze with the calibration program for Wroxi.

 When all the calibration standards are measured, the calibration curve can be adjusted.

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10.2.3 Controll of the accurracy for the new calibration:

Fuse new glass disks from the CRM materials, analyze them and evaluate the results.

10.3 Changing decimal delimiter for import of QAN-files to LIMS.

Never change an original QAN-file. Copy all the QAN-files that should be imported to the folder "Starlims import" on the desktop, and make changes in the copied files only.

The decimal delimiter must be changed from period (".") to comma (";") before data can be imported to LIMS.

All samples analyzed by WROXI are exported as a QAN-file to the "Results" folder on the desktop. The files are not named by the sample number. To check the identity of the files, they must be opened.

Files are most easily opened using notepad or notepad++.

Select all files for which the decimal delimiter should be changed, right click and chose *Edit* with *Notepad++*.

Select:

- *Search -> Replace...*
- *Find what: .*
- *Replace with: ;*
- *Select Replace all in all open documents*
- *Click Close.*
- *Select File -> Save All*

10.4 Back-up

Data are backed upp to an external hard drive every Friday. Additional backups should be done before every service or changes in the data system.

11 REFERENCES

APP002 Instrument instruction XRF instrument ZETIUM.